

Reactions at the Surface of Hot Metallic Filaments.
Part IV. The Reaction $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}$, on
Tungsten and Thoriated Tungsten.

By B. S. SRIKANTAN.

In the preceding parts (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 931), it has been shown that the interaction of carbon dioxide and hydrogen is to a large extent dependent on the nature of the surface catalysing it. Surfaces which presented a fused or sintered appearance were feebly active compared with fresh surfaces. All these lend support to Taylor's view of active centres (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1925, 108 A, 105), being mainly responsible for catalysis. In continuation this reaction has been studied on the surfaces of tungsten and thoriated tungsten. The interaction of carbon dioxide and hydrogen on tungsten has been studied by Prichard and Hinshelwood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1546). But the results described here are more elaborate and contain additional information on the nature of the reaction at the surface of tungsten.

The experimental arrangement was exactly the same as that in the previous parts. The catalyst was a tungsten filament taken from an Osram lamp (106 volts, 60 watts). It was about 60 cm. long and 0.001 cm. in diameter. The optical pyrometer was used to determine the temperatures. A few gas analyses have been performed to show that the reaction is only $\text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and that there is no complication. In the first few experiments it was seen that the resistance of the wire slowly changed such that its temperature changed from 948° to 965° without any adjustment. In the course of these experiments it was also noticed that light blue streaks of tungsten in regular lines corresponding to the shadow of the filament were deposited on the cool sides of the reaction vessel. This is perhaps due to the volatilisation of tungsten as carbonyl which decomposes, depositing tungsten when it comes in contact with the cool sides of the reaction vessel. After this, the deposit did not grow denser and the resistance of the wire was remarkably steady and the results were reproducible. Table I describes the results at 965°.

TABLE I.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 100.8 \text{ mm.}$		$P_{\text{H}_2} = 103.5 \text{ mm.}$		Temperature = 965° .	
Time (sec.).	Total press (mm.).	Unimolecular constant.			
0	204.3	—			
300	190.5	0.000476			
600	179.0	0.000467			
900	169.0	0.000462			
1200	160.2	0.000462			
1500	152.5	0.000462			
1800	146.0	0.000460			
2100	104.4	0.000460			
		Mean	0.0004600		

To make sure that no other reaction is proceeding except $\text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}$, a sample of gas from the last experiment, when the reaction had gone to about 70%, was taken and analysed. Table II shows that no other reaction except the one mentioned is taking place.

TABLE II.

Percentage composition ...	CO_2	CO	H_2	CH_4
By analysis ...	21.09	55.83	23.00	Nil.
By calculation ...	20.99	55.96	23.05	—

Influence of Temperature.—The following table gives the velocity constants at different temperatures with 100 mm. of each of the reacting gases.

TABLE III.

Temperature ...	1060°	1080°	1100°	1280°
Unimol. constant ...	0.00218	0.00280	0.00310	0.00520

Table IV gives the heats of activation and the temperature coefficients calculated from the above tables.

TABLE IV.

Temperature range ...	965° — 1080°	1060° — 1100°	1100° — 1280°
Temp. coeff. for 10° ...	1.18	1.09	1.03
Heat of activation (in cal.) ...	54,000	20,000	9,700

The temperature coefficient and the heat of activation fall off with rise of temperature. Similar observations have been recorded in the previous parts (*loc. cit.*). Taylor and Wesely (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 216) obtained similar results on the reaction between hydrogen sulphide and sulphur dioxide at glass surfaces. This interesting point will be explained at the end of the paper.

Influence of Pressure of Hydrogen on the Reaction.—Experiments were conducted

with 100 mm. of carbon dioxide and varying amounts of hydrogen at a temperature of 1060°. In Table III are given the data for the reaction with equal quantities of the gases. The following tables give the other values. The rate of reaction rapidly increases with the pressure of hydrogen

(Fig. 1). In the following tables, the velocity constants have been calculated with reference to carbon dioxide.

TABLE V.

Temperature = 1060°.

$P_{CO_2} = 100.5$ mm. $P_{H_2} = 222.2$ mm. $CO_2 : H_2 = 1 : 2$.

Time (sec.)	...	0	30	60	90	120	150	180
Total press. (mm.)	...	323.3	305.8	291.3	278.3	268.0	259.5	252.0
Press. of CO_2 (mm.)	...	100.5	83.0	68.5	55.5	45.2	36.7	29.8
Unimol. constant	...		0.0064	0.0064	0.0066	0.0066	0.0067	0.0067

Mean 0.0066

TABLE VI.

Temperature = 1060°.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 104.5 \text{ mm.}$		$P_{\text{H}_2} = 315.8 \text{ mm.}$		$\text{CO}_2 : \text{H}_2 = 1:3.$	
Time (sec.).	Total press. (mm.).	Press. of CO_2 (mm.).	Unimol. const.		
0	420.3	104.5			
* —	411.1	95.3			
30	385.9	70.1		0.0102	
60	367.5	51.7		0.0102	
90	352.4	36.6		0.0106	
120	340.6	24.8		0.0113	
150	332.1	16.3		0.0116	
300	317.0	1.2			
480	309.3				
780	308.0				
1080	298.5				
2880	260.8				

If the reaction is simply a reduction of carbon dioxide to carbon monoxide as represented by $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \longrightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}$, it is to be expected that the reaction would stop at about 300 sec., (cf. Table VI) when all the carbon dioxide has been used up. But it is seen that the pressure in the system decreases slowly even after 300 sec. in the above experiment. It is possible that another reaction is taking place between carbon monoxide and hydrogen towards the end of the reaction between carbon dioxide and hydrogen. Perhaps this is responsible for the slight rise in the velocity constants towards the end. An analysis of the gas at the end showed the presence of carbon monoxide and hydrogen but not of carbon dioxide. There was the test for the presence of methane of about 2 to 3 per cent. Since the experimental error in the analysis might also be about 2 per cent. it was not taken as conclusive evidence for the presence of methane.

A reaction was carried out with equal quantities of the reacting gases at 1060°, to completion and 100 mm. of hydrogen was put into the system, so that only equal quantities of carbon monoxide and hydrogen remained. No reaction was found to take place. Results similar to those described in Table VI were obtained with 1:4 and 1:5 of carbon dioxide and hydrogen. In both the cases the reaction was allowed to proceed for a long time after the usual limit and the gases analysed. Tests for methane to about 6 to 8 per cent. were obtained. Several analyses were made to detect the

* Time was not noted in the preliminary adjustment of temperature.

presence of methane. The quantities obtained varied with experiments, usually between 5 to 8 per cent. The maximum amount of methane obtained was 8.5 per cent. The production of methane seems to be peculiar and has an important bearing on the mechanism of the reaction. This point will be fully dealt with later. Tables VII and VIII refer to these experiments.

TABLE VII.

Temperature = 1060°.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 103.8 \text{ mm.}$	$P_{\text{H}_2} = 411.3 \text{ mm.}$	$\text{CO}_2 : \text{H}_2 = 1 : 4.$					
Time (sec.)	...	0	15	30	46	63	78
Total press. (mm.)	...	515.1	494.0	477.0	462.7	450.6	441.1
Press. of CO_2 (mm.)	...	103.8	82.7	65.7	51.4	39.3	29.8
Unimol. constant			0.0151	0.0152	0.0153	0.0154	0.0160
						Mean	0.0154

The rest of the data is not given here, for those in Tables VI and VII are sufficient to illustrate the above point.

TABLE VIII.

Temperature = 1060°.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 101.0 \text{ mm.}$	$P_{\text{H}_2} = 505.8 \text{ mm.}$	$\text{CO}_2 : \text{H}_2 = 1 : 5$	
Time (sec.).	Total press. (mm.).	Pressure of CO_2 (mm.).	Unimol. const.
0	606.8	101.0	
15	589.8	78.0	0.0172
45	554.0	49.2	0.0164
60	541.2	35.4	0.0178
75	531.8	26.0	0.0180
105	519.6	19.8	0.0189
135	512.0	6.2	
255	503.8		
555	495.5		
855	480.4		
3255	453.9		
6255	429.0		

A complete analysis of the gas in the reaction vessel from the previous experiment (Table VIII) is given here.

	C, H, etc.	CO ₂	CO	H ₂	CH ₄	Total
Percentage composition ...			24.9	66.5	8.5	99.9

Influence of Pressure of Carbon dioxide on the Reaction rate.—Experiments were performed with 100 mm. of hydrogen and varying amounts of carbon dioxide at 1060°. In Table III are given the velocity constants with 1:1 of hydrogen and carbon dioxide. The following tables give the other values. The reaction at first rises with increase of carbon dioxide till 200 mm. and then falls down to a steady low value. In the following tables the velocity constants are calculated with reference to hydrogen.

TABLE IX.

Temperature = 1060°.

 $P_{\text{CO}_2} = 211.4 \text{ mm.}$ $P_{\text{H}_2} = 105.5 \text{ mm.}$ $\text{CO}_2:\text{H}_2 = 2:1$

Time (sec.)	Total press. (mm.)	Pressure of H ₂ (mm.)	Unimolecular constant.
0	316.9	105.5	
* 15	296.4	85.0	
60	280.1	69.0	0.00469
90	271.0	59.8	0.00469
120	263.5	52.8	0.00460
150	256.4	45.2	0.00467
			Mean 0.00466

TABLE X.

Temperature = 1060°.

 $P_{\text{CO}_2} = 258.1 \text{ mm.}$ $P_{\text{H}_2} = 101.2 \text{ mm.}$ $\text{CO}_2:\text{H}_2 = 2.5:1.$

Time (sec.)	...	0	† 60	90	120	150	180	210
Total press. (mm.)	...	359.3	343.9	333.0	324.8	315.9	308.1	303.5
Press. of hydrogen (mm.)	...	101.2	85.8	74.9	66.7	57.7	50.0	44.4
Unimol. constant	...			0.0045	0.0042	0.0042	0.0045	0.0046
							Mean	0.0044

* Temperature was on the high side to start with and hence it is left out of consideration.

† Temperature on the high side to start with.

TABLE XI.

Temperature = 1060°.

	$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 308.8 \text{ mm.}$	$P_{\text{H}_2} = 100.7 \text{ mm.}$	$\text{CO}_2 : \text{H}_2 = 8 : 1.$			
Time (sec.)	...	0	60	120	180	240
Total press. (mm.)	...	404.0	385.5	370.8	358.9	349.8
Pressure of hydrogen	...	100.7	89.2	67.5	55.6	46.5
Unimolecular constant	...		0.00838	0.00834	0.00830	0.00830
						Mean 0.00833

Experiments with carbon dioxide together with four and five times the amount of hydrogen gave the same velocity constants as with 300 mm. of carbon dioxide. The average velocity constant was 0.00833.

The results from the above tables are represented in Fig. 1.

The reaction velocity increases linearly with the pressure of hydrogen. But with carbon dioxide the reaction velocity at first increases slightly, then comes down and remains constant with further increase of carbon dioxide. There is a maximum at about 200 mm. Thus it is evident that the adsorption of hydrogen increases with pressure. But in the case of carbon dioxide the active surface is saturated even below 200 mm. A further increase of CO_2 results in a slight displacement of hydrogen from the surface. But Prichard and Hinshelwood (*loc. cit.*) observed slightly different effects. It was noted by them, however, that saturation for CO_2 was reached at lower pressures than with hydrogen and at higher pressures a slight displacement of hydrogen by carbon dioxide was noted.

It appears therefore that both the reactants are adsorbed on the surface independently of each other. This view is confirmed by the following considerations.

The Active Surface covered with Hydrogen.—The following table has been constructed from the data described above.

TABLE XII.

	$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 100 \text{ mm.}$	Temperature = 1060°.				
Pressure of hydrogen (mm.)	...	102	228	318	411	508
Percentage of CO_2 converted into CO in 100 sec.	...	26	48	67	83	85

Let θ_{H_2} be the fraction of the active surface covered with hydrogen.

Then the adsorption equilibrium is expressed by a simple formula, the percentage conversion of carbon dioxide into carbon monoxide in 100 seconds is taken as proportional to the reaction rate.

$$k_1 (1-\theta) [\text{H}_2] = k_2 \theta, \quad \text{where } [\text{H}_2] = \text{the pressure of hydrogen; } k_1 \text{ and } k_2 \text{ are constants.}$$

$$\therefore \theta = \frac{[\text{H}_2]}{k_2/k_1 + [\text{H}_2]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

Let x be the limiting rate at saturation hydrogen pressure.

Then the part of the active surface covered at any pressure is also the ratio of the reaction rate at that pressure to the limiting rate. Thus

$$\theta = [\text{H}_2]/x,$$

$$\text{if } [\text{H}_2] = 102, \quad \theta = 25/x.$$

$$\text{if } [\text{H}_2] = 223, \quad \theta = 48/x.$$

Substituting for θ in (1) and solving

$$x = 214; \quad k_2/k_1 = 771.$$

Then

$$\theta_{\text{H}_2} = \frac{[\text{H}_2]}{771 + [\text{H}_2]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

The following table gives the fraction of the active surface covered with hydrogen at various pressures. $\theta_{\text{cal.}}$ is the value calculated from the equation (2) and $\theta_{\text{obs.}}$ is calculated on the assumption that the ratio of the reaction rate at any pressure to that at limiting rate gives the active surface covered at that pressure. They both agree well.

TABLE XIII.

Pressure of hydrogen (mm.)	...	102	223	316	411	506
$\theta_{\text{cal.}}$	...	0.12	0.23	0.31	0.36	0.41
$\theta_{\text{obs.}}$	...	0.12	0.22	0.29	0.35	0.40

The Active Surface covered with Carbon Dioxide.—The surface is saturated with carbon dioxide even below 200 mm. The following table shows that the limiting rate at saturation pressure is 29 mm. The fraction of the active surface covered with carbon dioxide is given by the expression,—

$$\theta_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{[\text{CO}_2]}{16 + [\text{CO}_2]}$$

TABLE XIV.

$P_{\text{H}_2} = 100 \text{ mm.}$		Temperature = 1060°.					
Press. of CO_2 (mm.)	...	103	212	258	303	408	534
Percentage of CO formed in 100 secs.	...	25	48	30	29	29	29
θ cal.	...	0.86	0.93	0.94	0.95	0.96	0.97
θ obs.	...	0.86	1.7	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0

The Kinetics of the Reaction.—If the gases are adsorbed on the active centres of the surface, independent of each other, it is evident that the reaction rate at any pressure of the gases ought to be a function of the surface covered by hydrogen and also carbon dioxide.

$$\text{Reaction rate} = k \cdot \theta_{\text{H}_2} \theta_{\text{CO}_2}$$

where k is a constant, θ_{H_2} , θ_{CO_2} , active surfaces covered by H_2 and CO_2 respectively.

Taking the reaction rate as measured by the amount of carbon monoxide formed in 100 secs., the constancy of k can be tested by substituting the data in the above relation. For θ_{H_2} and θ_{CO_2} the observed values from the above table have been used.

TABLE XV.

$P_{\text{CO}_2} = 100 \text{ mm.}$		$\text{Temperature } 1060^\circ.$	$P_{\text{H}_2} = 100 \text{ mm.}$	
P_{H_2} (mm.).	k		P_{CO_2} (mm.).	k
102	240		108	240
223	240		212	240
316	250		258	250
411	280		303	240
506	250		408	240
			534	240

The idea of independent adsorption of CO_2 and H_2 on the active centres is supported. The reaction seems to proceed through the adsorption of both the gases side by side on the active centres.

The Surface of the Wire.—The fresh wire had a metallic lustre while the wire after use had a dull appearance. Microscopic examination of the surface (Fig. 2) shows that this surface which was smooth has become uneven and pitted after the reaction. This is mostly due perhaps to the volatilisation of tungsten as carbonyl. The shadows on the cool sides of the vessel point to this conclusion. Further the adsorption of the reacting gases on the surface might be of a chemical nature such that the disengagement of the reaction products might involve breaking up of the surface complex and consequent alteration in the nature of the surface.

After Before
FIG. 2.

The Mechanism of the Reaction.—In a system containing a number of gases like CO , CO_2 and H_2 , it might be expected that the reaction would be very complicated giving various reactions as:—

It is rather surprising that the reaction studied is not so complex but proceeds as $\text{CO}_2 + \text{H}_2 \rightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CO}$.

Armstrong and Hilditch (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1928, 103A 25) state that the reduction of carbon dioxide by hydrogen at the surface of nickel goes directly to methane and gives no carbon monoxide: so that partial reduction is not taking place. "This is at variance with some observations made in the laboratories of the Munitions department in England, during the War, where methane prepared from CO_2 and H_2 contained small percentages of CO" (Rideal and Taylor, "Catalysis in theory and practice," 1926, p. 166, 252).

The results described in the previous tables where the ratio of $\text{H}_2:\text{CO}_2$ is more than 2:1, throw some light on the mechanism of the reduction of CO_2 by H_2 . There is a slow reaction taking place almost at the end of the usual reaction. Gas analysis showed a small percentage of methane. Several careful analyses were performed. The maximum amount of methane obtained was 8.5 per cent. It is possible to explain the formation of small amounts of methane thus:—

On adding (2) and (3) it comes to the same as (1). It is just possible that as soon as some methane is formed in the presence of carbon dioxide the methane will all be oxidised according to (3). Hence ordinarily no test for methane is got and the sum total of the reactions is as (1). But with excess of hydrogen in the reaction mixture (*cf.* Tables VI to VIII) towards the end when all the carbon dioxide is used up, there is a tendency for methane to accumulate in the system, and hence a slow fall in the pressure is noted. The gas analysis shows the presence of methane: probably a slow reaction represented by (4) is taking place between carbon monoxide and hydrogen. Such a reaction is also possible even in the beginning as soon as some carbon monoxide is formed but then the methane will again be oxidised in the presence of CO_2 (3).

It appeared therefore that the first stage in the reduction of CO_2 is CH_4 . The usual reaction is the sum of a series of fast reactions taking place simultaneously.

The possibility of two or more concurrent reactions proceeding at the same time is supported by the experiments on the temperature coefficient of this reaction on this and other wires (*cf.* previous parts). The temperature coefficient and the energy of activation fall off with rise of temperature (*cf.* also Taylor and Wesely, *loc. cit.*). This variation does not arise from the change in the uniformity of the wire and temperature, since these readings have been taken only after the wire was known to be steady and the experiments have been duplicated working at higher and lower temperatures alternately.

In the event of two reactions proceeding at the same time, if the

Fig. 3.

logarithms of the reaction velocity be plotted against the reciprocal of the absolute temperature, one ought not to get a straight line, which would be the case if Arrhenius' equation held good (C. N. Hinshelwood, "Kinetics of Chemical Change in Gaseous Systems", 1926, p. 446). Graphs plotted for $\log K$ and $1/T$ show that straight lines are not obtained. Fig. 3 gives the graph for tungsten wire. This supports the idea that the reaction

studied is made up of more than a single one and whose temperature coefficients are not the same.

Thoriated Tungsten.

A few experiments were next conducted with thoriated tungsten wire as the catalyst, with 100 mm. of each of the gases.

The activity of the wire slowly decreased with use till it came to a low value, where it was steady afterwards. On raising the temperature of the reactions, the wire was again unsteady but gave reproducible results after some use at that temperature. But again working at the lower temperature it did not give the same values as before. The wire was found to have been deactivated to a considerable extent. The wire was heated in vacuum and this again reduced its activity to a considerable extent. But at any temperature it came to a steady

value only after some use: working alternately at high and low temperatures again changed the activity.

At 925° the reaction velocity fell gradually from 0·000507 to 0·000300 where it was steady. At 1025° it fell from 0·000658 to 0·000344 ; but working again at 925° the velocity was only 0·000152. Heating the wire in vacuum and working again at 1025° gave values of 0·00180 only.

The surface of the wire before and after the reaction is similar to that of tungsten.

Summary and Conclusions.

1. The interaction between carbon dioxide and hydrogen has been studied at the surface of tungsten. The wire is steady in activity after some use.
 2. The temperature coefficient of the reaction and the energy of activation fall down with rise of temperature.
 3. The reaction velocity increases with the pressure of hydrogen.
 4. The fraction of the active surface covered with hydrogen at various pressures has been calculated.
 5. The surface becomes saturated with carbon dioxide even below 200 mm. pressure and the reaction velocity does not change with further increase of carbon dioxide except for a very slight extent at 200 mm, which is perhaps due to the slight displacement of hydrogen.
 6. The reaction proceeds through the adsorption of both the gases on the surface without prejudice to each other.
 7. The reaction between carbon dioxide and hydrogen appears to take place through a series of rapid reactions, involving the production of methane and its consequent oxidation to carbonmonoxide by carbon dioxide.
 8. The surface of the wire is changed to a decided extent after the reaction.
 9. The reaction has also been studied at the surface of thoriated tungsten. The wire was not found to be steady in activity.
- In conclusion I wish to express my sincere thanks to Professor H. E. Watson for his kind interest and helpful criticism.

